

Digital Public Infrastructure as Pillars of National Cybersecurity: Strategic Responses to India's Cyber Threat Environment

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Abstract

This paper is a conceptual contribution to cybersecurity governance, outlining India's DPI as a voluntary, ex-ante model driven by network effects, distinct from traditional mandatory regimes like China's Multi-Level Protection Scheme (MLPS) or the EU's Network and Information Security Directive (NIS2).. Its aim is not a forensic audit of DPI's security but to articulate its design principles and comparative resilience, laying groundwork for future study. This paper outlines DPI's security framework—security architectures, interoperability-based enforcement, policy/governance and compliance regimes, and user-controlled obfuscation—through systems like Aadhaar, UPI, and ABDM. Comparative case studies (e.g., SingHealth, SSN breaches) highlight DPI's resilience at population scale, mitigating risks that plague centralized systems. We rely on official sources—to define DPI's framework, reflecting its state-driven nature. Unlike punitive ex-post frameworks, DPI incentivizes security via market dynamics: entities join voluntarily, facing exclusion from ubiquitous networks if non-compliant, a pressure amplified by India's new Digital Personal Data Protection Act (DPDP), 2023. Prior to the DPDP, DPI ecosystem policies functioned as *pseudo-laws*, embedding breach notification, security certification, and compliance standards. Post-DPDP, this regime aligns with statutory oversight, countering external breaches and U.S. resistance to India's data protection efforts. While breaches outside DPI's regulated ecosystem expose gaps, they underscore its design logic—pushing entities toward compliance. This paper details DPI's principles and comparative strengths, not as a definitive assessment but as a foundation for critical research into its efficacy, adoption

challenges, and interplay with statutory oversight. It posits DPI as a scalable alternative for nations balancing digital sovereignty and security, inviting scrutiny of its real-world impact.

Introduction

The UN Envoy on Technology highlights DPI’s role in managing “accountable interplay of services” without harm.¹ India’s DPI—Aadhaar, UPI, ABDM—exemplifies this at scale, serving 1.4 billion citizens. Beyond inclusion, DPI blends a *voluntary policy regime with robust security architectures*, countering cybercrime surge and state-sponsored threats in ways distinct from mandatory regimes in the US, EU, and China. *This paper targets policymakers crafting resilient digital ecosystems and researchers probing hybrid governance and design*, investigating DPI as a strategic response leveraging ecosystem scale and technical innovation.

Traditional cybersecurity splits into ex-ante mandates (e.g., EU’s NIS2 audits) and ex-post penalties (e.g., US FTC fines). *India’s DPI allowed voluntary entry—entities joined freely—but enforced security through network policies and architectures like federated data and masked IDs (NHA, 2023)*. Scaled by UPI’s 510 million monthly users (NPCI, 2024), this preceded and now aligns with the DPDP, 2023. Case studies

¹ Office of the United Nations Secretary-General’s Envoy on Technology & United Nations Development Programme. (2024). Leveraging DPI for safe and inclusive societies: Interim report. DPI Safeguards. <https://safedpi.gitbook.io/safeguards/about-the-universal-dpi-safeguards-initiative/key-outputs/interim-report-leveraging-dpi-for-safe-and-inclusive-societies>

highlight DPI's edge. Fortified cores (e.g., ABDM's ISO 27001 certification, NHA, 2023) and decentralized edges offer hybrid resilience.

This study's purpose is not to critique DPI's efficacy—prior work addresses its flaws—but to delineate its design as a voluntary alternative, highlighting its resilience at population scale and inviting further research. Section 2 defines DPI's governance model; Section 3 details its security principles; Section 4 examines Aadhaar and ABDM architectures; and Section 5 contrasts DPI with global breaches. The conclusion frames DPI as a blueprint for nations, underscoring areas—adoption, external risks—for future study. A methodology section clarifies our reliance on official sources to define this model, setting the stage for critical inquiry.

Methodology

This paper is a conceptual analysis of India's DPI as a voluntary cybersecurity governance model, driven by network effects. It aims not to audit DPI's security empirically but to articulate its design principles, governance regime and comparative resilience, inviting further study. We rely on official sources—to define DPI's framework, reflecting its state-led intent. These are supplemented by external reports and standards for triangulation, addressing source bias noted in prior critiques.

Case studies (SingHealth, MediSecure, RENAPER, SSN) serve as heuristics, contrasting DPI's mitigation features with known vulnerabilities, not as exhaustive benchmarks. Analysis draws on India's cyber threat context and DPDP, 2023, framing DPI's relevance as a network-effects driven, voluntary ex-ante novel digital governance

model. This approach prioritizes design and governance regime over performance, scoping the paper as a foundation for empirical research into DPI's efficacy, adoption gaps, and global potential.

Background

With the “rapid evolution” of threats fueled by sophistication of attackers and advancements in tactics, the global cyber threat environment is heightened.² India's digital era coincides with heightened cyber threats—government attacks rose 95% in 2022.³ India ranks 14th in breach costs and faces persistent risks.⁴

DPI—Aadhaar (identity), UPI (payments), ABDM (health)—anchors India's response. Aadhaar reduces fraud via biometric IDs; UPI enables real-time transfers; ABDM digitizes healthcare with consent-based sharing. Unlike mandatory ex-ante (e.g., China's MLPS) or ex-post (e.g., US FTC) regimes, DPI imposes voluntary security burdens, cutting interoperability for non-compliance. This market-driven model, scaled by network effects, aligns with India's G20 push⁵ and DPDP, 2023, offering a blueprint for digital sovereignty.

² NordLayer. (2024). *Cybersecurity evolution: How cyber threats have changed over the last 10 years*. Retrieved from <https://nordlayer.com/blog/evolution-of-cyber-threats-over-10-years/>.

³ CloudSEK. (2022). *Unprecedented increase in cyber attacks targeting government entities in 2022*. CloudSEK.

https://uploads-ssl.webflow.com/635e632477408d12d1811a64/63d39e6ee68d87e7d6c799bf_Unprecedented-Increase-in-Cyber-Attacks-Targeting-Government-Entities-in-2022.pdf

⁴ Press Information Bureau, Government of India. (2024, February 15). <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2003505>

⁵ Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (n.d.). Report of India's G20 Task Force on Digital Public Infrastructure. DEA. <https://dea.gov.in/sites/default/files/Report%20of%20Indias%20G20%20Task%20Force%20On%20Digital%20Public%20Infrastructure.pdf>

Cybersecurity Analysis

In response to the heightened cyber threat environment, a number of states have instituted security governance regimes for digital services in their domestic markets. Many of the regimes instituted focus on Ex Post compliance, i.e., acting upon a violation after a violation has occurred. At the same time, some jurisdictions, such as the People's Republic of China (PRC) and the European Union (EU) have instituted mandatory Ex Ante measures, instituting licensing and certification requirements for digital services prior to going live.

- International Regimes on Cybersecurity:

- **PRC:**

The PRC's approach to cybersecurity emphasises ex ante compliance through a security licensing regime. Enabled by a host of laws and regulations, the PRC's cybersecurity governance regime requires entities seeking to offer digital services to demonstrate compliance prior to going live, while imposing penalties for non compliance through fines, license revocations, blacklisting and state takeovers.

While the Cybersecurity Law, 2017⁶ focuses on establishing security obligations and penalties for violation, the Multi-Level Protection Scheme (MLPS 2.0) classifies IT systems into five levels based on their perceived

⁶ DigiChina. (2017, June 1). *Translation: Cybersecurity Law of the People's Republic of China (Effective June 1, 2017)*. Stanford University. <https://digichina.stanford.edu/work/translation-cybersecurity-law-of-the-peoples-republic-of-china-effective-june-1-2017/>

risk to national security, public welfare, and economic stability, with increasingly stringent security requirements at each level. For higher risk levels, the MPLS 2.0 imposes licensing requirements for entities prior to going live. A key ex ante facet of MPLS licensing is a government sanctioned cybersecurity assessment for systems classified as being higher risk.⁷

- **United States of America:**

The US has instituted a number of Ex Ante measures such as the NIST⁸ standards but these are voluntary in nature, while being required to do business with the federal government. At the same time, the US' consumer protection regime, through agencies like the Federal Trade Commission (FTC), has instituted a regime of Ex Post measures including fines which can be levied on violators including fines.

- **European Union:**

The EU's security governance regime includes a number of Ex Ante measures while emphasising Ex Post penalties. Under the Network and

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<https://www.reedsmith.com/en/perspectives/2019/10/mlps-20-chinas-enhanced-data-security-multi-level-protection>

⁸ **National Institute of Standards and Technology. (n.d.).** *NIST: Advancing measurement science, standards, and technology.* U.S. Department of Commerce. Retrieved February 15, 2025, from <https://www.nist.gov/>

Information Security 2 (NIS2) Directive⁹ and the Cyber Resilience Act¹⁰, entities operating in critical sectors must register with their national cybersecurity agencies and undergo periodic audits. Failure to comply can result in fines and restriction of business operations in EU markets.

DPI's ex-ante approach embeds security into participation, not mandates. Where centralization occurs—e.g., ABDM's core infrastructure—it meets global standards like ISO 27001, mandating risk assessments and encryption (ISO/IEC 27001:2013). This ensures fortified cores support federated edges, unlike the reactive penalties of US frameworks or PRC's rigid controls. Interoperability enforces compliance: participants adopt standards to join, with exclusion as the penalty—e.g., 90% of Indian banks use UPI, sidelining non-compliant players. This hybrid design—voluntary yet fortified—distinguishes DPI, as its architectures reveal.

⁹ European Parliament & Council of the European Union. (2022, December 27). *Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2 Directive)*. Official Journal of the European Union. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2555/oj/eng>

¹⁰ **European Commission. (2024).** *Cyber Resilience Act*. Retrieved February 15, 2025, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cyber-resilience-act>

DPI as a State-Orchestrated, Network Effects-Driven and Market-Oriented Voluntary Security Governance Regime

India's Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI) redefines cybersecurity governance through a voluntary, market-oriented approach, leveraging technology to secure societal systems without mandatory edicts. Some key examples of DPI ecosystems include:

1. **Aadhaar:**

Aadhaar is India's unique biometric identification system, providing a 12-digit unique identity number to residents. It serves as the foundation for various public services and welfare programs, ensuring accurate identification and reducing fraud. Aadhaar's robust security features are enforced across all licence holders, raising the security bar for data protection nationwide.

2. **ABDM (Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission):**

ABDM seeks to digitise India's healthcare ecosystem by establishing a unified digital health infrastructure. It enables secure, consent-based data sharing across healthcare providers, enhancing patient care and streamlining healthcare delivery. ABDM leverages a decentralised model to ensure data privacy and security.

3. **UPI** (Unified Payments Interface):

UPI revolutionises digital payments in India by enabling instant, real-time money transfers between bank accounts via mobile devices. It supports peer-to-peer transactions, bill payments, and merchant payments, making digital transactions accessible and efficient for millions of users across the country

Central to DPI is voluntary participation: entities join to access benefits (e.g., Aadhaar authentication, UPI transactions), adhering to security standards and compliance regimes as a condition. Authentication User Agencies (AUAs) and KYC User Agencies (KUAs) in Aadhaar, for instance, must adopt encryption and audits to participate (UIDAI, n.d.). Network effects amplify this: as adoption grows, exclusion becomes a de facto penalty. A non-compliant UPI provider loses interoperability with a network handling 60% of global digital transactions, rendering it unattractive. This contrasts with punitive regimes—e.g., PRC’s licensing—where compliance is enforced ex-ante via law, or the US’s ex-post fines.

The Aadhaar ecosystem exemplifies this. Non-licensed entities, rely on physical cards without CIDR verification, risking fraud from fake submissions. This nudges them toward licensure, embedding security via participation—a dynamic bolstered by the Digital Personal Data Protection Act (DPDP), 2023, which mandates data protection for all fiduciaries, aligning legal and market pressures. Centralized components anchor this model: ABDM’s core infrastructure, for instance, aligns with ISO 27001, a global standard for information security management (NHA, 2023).

DPI's governance thus balances federated edges with fortified cores, using scale and interdependence, not coercion. Open APIs and standardization ensure interoperability, while voluntary standards "embed legal obligations into code" (DEA, n.d.). This hybrid resilience—market-driven at scale, secured globally at the center—sets the stage for the security principles that follow.

DPI's Role in India's Security Governance Regime: Pre- and Post-DPDP

India's Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI)—an "infrastructure-based approach" leveraging technology, markets, and governance¹¹—redefines cybersecurity governance through a voluntary, state-orchestrated regime that countered U.S. pressure on the Personal Data Protection Bill (PDP Bill),¹² bridging to the Digital Personal Data Protection Act (DPDP, 2023). Ecosystems like Aadhaar, UPI, and ABDM embed security by placing the burden on data fiduciaries (DFs) and granting citizen rights, aligning with and exceeding DPDP through "compliance by the mere act of participation."¹³

Pre-DPDP: A Fiduciary-Driven Bypass Amid U.S. Pressure

Pre-DPDP, India's "untamed" cyber landscape faced a crime surge. India's efforts to enact a comprehensive data protection regime through the PDP Bill led to resistance by

¹¹ Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (n.d.). *Report of India's G20 Task Force on Digital Public Infrastructure*.

DEA. <https://dea.gov.in/sites/default/files/Report%20of%20Indias%20G20%20Task%20Force%20On%20Digital%20Public%20Infrastructure.pdf>

¹² Office of the United States Trade Representative. (2019, March). *Fact sheet on the 2019 National Trade Estimate Report on Foreign Trade Barriers*. U.S. Trade Representative.

<https://ustr.gov/about-us/policy-offices/press-office/fact-sheets/2019/march/fact-sheet-2019-national-trade-estimate>

¹³ Parsheera, S. (2022). India's policy responses to big tech: And an eye on the rise of 'alt big tech'. *Indian Journal of Law and Technology*, 18(1).

the U.S.¹⁴ DPI bypassed this with voluntary network policies that "civilized" the ecosystem. Participation was optional—no IT Act amendment compelled entry—but binding rules enforced security.

Comparing ABDM's Health Data Management Policy with the Draft PDP Bill, ChatGPT assigns a similarity score of 8.5/10 across Fiduciary obligations, Principal rights, consent requirements, governance of sensitive personal data, Grievance Redressal, Data Security Safeguards, Governance of Children's Data, and provisions relating to nominees and emergencies. Annexure 1a highlights these similarities.

When dealing specifically with security governance surrounding General Security Obligations, Data Minimization, De-identification & Anonymisation, Privacy and Security by Design, Audit compliances, Data Breach Management, Retention & Storage Limitation, Processor Obligations and Encryption / Technical Standards, ChatGPT assigned a similarity score of 9/10. Annexure 1b discusses this in depth.

DPI ecosystems leveraged Network effects through scale to drive compliance: non-adherence risked interoperability loss, nudging entities into a regulated fold. Architectures like federated data and SOCs have limited breach scope, contrasting with China's MLPS or EU's NIS2 mandatory regimes.

Post-DPDP: Alignment and Exceedance

¹⁴ Office of the United States Trade Representative. (2019, March). *Fact sheet on the 2019 National Trade Estimate Report on Foreign Trade Barriers*. U.S. Trade Representative. <https://ustr.gov/about-us/policy-offices/press-office/fact-sheets/2019/march/fact-sheet-2019-national-trade-estimate>

The DPDP aligns with DPI's pre-existing framework, codifying fiduciary burdens and rights. At the same time, DPI exceeds DPDP via participation: joining enforces standards "embedded into code"¹⁵—e.g., federated designs, data vaults—beyond DPDP's legal floor. Non-compliant AUAs lose verification access; UPI PSPs risk irrelevance.

Security Principles of DPIs

- Network Effects Driven Voluntary Compliance Regime

A key feature of India's DPI journey is its voluntary nature. Entities are not compelled by law to participate in DPI ecosystems. Rather, participants are free to enter or exit DPI ecosystems at will.

The voluntary nature of DPI ecosystems sets them apart from traditional digital governance regimes which compel entities into compliance. While time consuming, once DPI ecosystems scale, they achieve network effects,¹⁶ where enough participants are transacting on these ecosystems that their presence in contemporary life becomes ubiquitous. Once network effects are realised, participants are incentivised to participate in DPI ecosystems.

¹⁵Rahul Matthan. (2023, May). *What is the DPI approach?* Trilegal. <https://trilegal.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/What-Is-the-DPI-Approach.pdf>

¹⁶ Stobierski, T. (2020, November 12). *What are network effects?*. Business Insights Blog. <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/what-are-network-effects>

A key distinction to be made is the case of Aadhar which is compulsory for certain functionality like banking from a citizen perspective. However, even in the case of Aadhar, Requesting Entities outside the compulsory Aadhar can opt to use Aadhaar as an identifier for authentication of e-KYC.

- **Interoperability as an enforcement mechanism**

A key feature of DPI and Open Networks is the penalty framework. Due to the voluntary nature of the aforementioned ecosystems, participants found in violation of security policies cannot be fined and their business licenses cannot be cancelled by the ecosystem administrators.

Au contraire, DPI and Open Networks rely on excluding violating entities from their networks, limiting interoperability. In practice, this regime implies that violating entities can continue their business operations, but due to limited interoperability in DPI ecosystems, which have achieved network effects through scale, the market attractiveness of such solutions is significantly reduced. In essence, DPI ecosystems leverage a key facet of interdependence, the ability of central nodes to cut off access to the larger network¹⁷, to penalise non compliance with security obligations.

The DPI security governance regime, while not enforcing formal barriers to business operations as a result of security violations, incentivises compliance through directly affecting consumer perceptions. For example:

¹⁷ **Farrell, H., & Newman, A. L. (2019).** Weaponized interdependence: How global economic networks shape state coercion. *International Security*, 44(1), 42-79. https://doi.org/10.1162/isec_a_00351

- UPI Compliance: Payment service providers (PSPs) that fail to meet security benchmarks are excluded from interoperable payment networks, reducing their market attractiveness.
- ABDM:
- Aadhaar Ecosystem: Entities that fail to meet UIDAI's stringent authentication requirements lose access to Aadhaar-linked verification services, making them unviable in identity-dependent industries.

This approach ensures that security violations lead to market-driven deterrents rather than direct governmental intervention, fostering a self-correcting, resilient digital economy.

- Security by compartmentalisation - Federation and Cost of Compliance

India's approach to DPI is deeply rooted in the principle of security by compartmentalisation, which is embodied in its federated data architecture. This framework strategically decentralises the storage and processing of data, ensuring that information remains at the periphery—where it was originally collected—rather than being consolidated into a central repository. Such decentralisation serves to mitigate the significant risks posed by centralised data storage systems, which are vulnerable to large-scale breaches and misuse.¹⁸ By allowing data to remain distributed across the

¹⁸ Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (n.d.). *Report of India's G20 Task Force on Digital Public Infrastructure*. DEA. <https://dea.gov.in/sites/default/files/Report%20of%20Indias%20G20%20Task%20Force%20On%20Digital%20Public%20Infrastructure.pdf>

network's edges, India significantly reduces the potential for mass surveillance and data exploitation within its population-scale digital ecosystem.¹⁹

A model of this decentralised architecture is the Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission (ABDM), which boasts a federated system devoid of a centralised data repository. Instead, ABDM facilitates secure data exchange between stakeholders within the network, contingent on the explicit consent of the patient. The absence of centralised data storage is instrumental in ensuring that sensitive health information is not concentrated in a singular, easily compromised location, thereby bolstering the overall security posture of the ecosystem.²⁰

At the same time, critical functionalities within these infrastructures—such as identity verification through **Ayushman Bharat Health Account (ABHA) IDs**, **Health Professional IDs (HPID)**, and **Health Facility Registry IDs (HFR ID)**—are centralised to ensure heightened security. This centralisation is coupled with strict security compliance obligations, which apply predominantly to the core elements of the infrastructure, while relieving peripheral participants of the need for excessive compliance measures and enabling developers to focus on “consumer experiences and products” without the burden of “infrastructure, permissioning and access.”²¹ This strategic delineation between centralised and decentralised components enables a dual-layered security framework that is both robust and efficient.

¹⁹ Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (n.d.). *Report of India's G20 Task Force on Digital Public Infrastructure*. DEA. <https://dea.gov.in/sites/default/files/Report%20of%20Indias%20G20%20Task%20Force%20On%20Digital%20Public%20Infrastructure.pdf>

²⁰ Press Information Bureau, Government of India. (2023, July 27) National Digital Health Ecosystem . PIB. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1942715>

²¹ India Stack. (n.d.). Open networks. India Stack. <http://indiastack.org/open-networks.html>

The cost of compliance, particularly in this context, becomes a key consideration. The centralisation of identity-related processes, such as the generation of ABHA IDs, reduces the burden on developers and peripheral applications, which would otherwise have had to secure costly licences and meet rigorous compliance standards for accessing Aadhaar data directly. For instance, prior to the implementation of ABDM, developers were required to obtain an Authentication User Agency (AUA) or KYC User Agency (KUA) licence from the Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI), should they wish to leverage Aadhaar for creating unique health IDs. This process entailed substantial security compliance obligations, including audits and ongoing assessments. However, under the ABDM framework, the cost and compliance burden associated with Aadhaar integration are centralised, allowing developers to focus on “building the best consumer experiences and products instead of having to worry about infrastructure, permissioning, and access.”²²

The cost of leveraging Aadhaar as an identifier has similarly shifted away from the edge developers to central registries/gateways administrators. For instance, in the ABDM ecosystem, while ABHA is generated using citizen Aadhaar, the ABDM integrated applications require only a Web Application Security Assessment from a CERT-In empanelled agency to onboard. On the other hand, the NHA is subject to the ISO 27001 Information Security standard as well as the compliance burden imposed by NHA using UIDAI’s AUA/KUA licence.

This compartmentalisation of security responsibility, with centralisation of critical elements and decentralisation of peripheral components, not only reduces the overall

²² India Stack. (n.d.). Open networks. India Stack. <http://indiastack.org/open-networks.html>

cost of compliance but also streamlines the development and integration of applications within the broader DPI ecosystem. The result is a more secure and agile infrastructure, capable of supporting innovation while maintaining the highest levels of trust and compliance.

- Consented Data Sharing: 2FA

Frameworks governing consensual data transfer, such as India's Data Empowerment and Protection Architecture (DEPA), facilitate a myriad of applications that transcend various sectors. This approach reinforces individuals' ownership of their data, thereby fostering a culture of sharing across providers and enabling the development of bespoke products and services tailored to meet diverse needs.²³

In this context, consensual data sharing operates as an essential second factor in the establishment of two-factor authentication (2FA). Within the ambit of ABDM, the security architecture is designed such that even in the unfortunate event that a Health Information Provider (HIP) is compromised, the ensuing risks remain substantially contained. The decentralised nature of health information—stored at the edges of the network and distributed across multiple entities—means that an unauthorised individual would face the formidable challenge of breaching multiple HIPs simultaneously to access meaningful data. Moreover, the consent management for data sharing is overseen by the Health Information Exchange Consent Manager (HIE CM). Thus, in the event of an infiltration, an assailant would also be required to breach the HIE CM or a

²³Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (n.d.). *Report of India's G20 Task Force on Digital Public Infrastructure*. DEA. <https://dea.gov.in/sites/default/files/Report%20of%20Indias%20G20%20Task%20Force%20On%20Digital%20Public%20Infrastructure.pdf>

patient's Personal Health Record (PHR) application to obtain the requisite consent, thereby adding an additional layer of security that is paramount in safeguarding patient information.

Similarly, under the Aadhaar framework, authentication and electronic Know Your Customer (e-KYC) processes are activated only after securing explicit, two-factor authentication-based consent from the citizen. Further enhancing user agency, individuals possess the capacity to selectively restrict access to specific authentication modalities, including biometric data, associated with their Aadhaar number through the UIDAI's mobile application. By defaulting to the disabling of certain authentication methods and permitting their activation solely on a voluntary basis, the system effectively limits the potential misuse of biometric authentication, thereby enhancing the integrity of the two-factor authentication requirements.

In the domain of financial transactions, the UPI ecosystem exemplifies the implementation of multiple layers of security. Among its paramount features is the UPI PIN, which serves as an indispensable safeguard, mandating user consent for all debit transactions. This dual-layered security framework, comprising the UPI PIN alongside application-specific identifiers, establishes a formidable barrier against unauthorised access, ensuring that any potential breach would necessitate overcoming numerous protective layers.

- Ex Ante Regulation vs. Ex Post Security Regulation

In the contemporary discourse on DPI and Open Networks, the concept of Ex Ante or *A priori* regulation emerges as a critical framework, promoting proactive measures to ensure the security and integrity of digital applications before they are deployed. This forward-looking approach is embodied in the establishment of Sandbox environments, wherein applications are rigorously validated and integrated within DPI frameworks, thereby facilitating the widespread dissemination of digital innovations across the nation.²⁴

In contrast to the reactive nature of Ex Ante or *A posteriori* regulation, which imposes compliance standards only in the aftermath of security breaches or incidents, Ex Ante or *A priori* regulation within the DPI ecosystem mandates adherence to a collective set of minimum security requirements prior to operationalisation. Participants engaged in DPIs and Open Network ecosystems are thus voluntarily bound by these standards, fostering a culture of accountability and trust among stakeholders.²⁵

The implementation of Ex Ante or *A priori* regulation ensures that security measures are woven into the very fabric of participation in the digital ecosystem²⁶. For instance, in the

²⁴Press Information Bureau, Government of India. (2023, August 9). *Update on Digital Healthcare Platforms*. PIB. <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1944592>

²⁵Trilegal. (2023, May). *What is the DPI approach?* Trilegal. <https://trilegal.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/What-Is-the-DPI-Approach.pdf>

²⁶Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance, Government of India. (n.d.). *Report of India's G20 Task Force on Digital Public Infrastructure*. DEA. <https://dea.gov.in/sites/default/files/Report%20of%20Indias%20G20%20Task%20Force%20On%20Digital%20Public%20Infrastructure.pdf>

context of the ABDM, the generation of the Ayushman Bharat Health Account (ABHA), along with the Health Professional ID (HPID) and Health Facility Registry ID (HFR ID), occurs within a framework that prioritises security compliance before any application is activated on the network. This approach fundamentally shifts the paradigm of compliance, reinforcing the notion that adherence to security standards is a prerequisite for engagement in the ecosystem.

Moreover, the application of Ex Ante or *A priori* regulation significantly reduces the cost burden of compliance for network participants. By centralising critical functionalities and establishing a common security baseline, the regulatory framework alleviates the financial strain on peripheral applications, allowing developers to focus on innovation and enhancing user experience without the encumbrance of navigating complex regulatory requirements.

In stark contrast, Ex Post or *A posteriori* regulation often places the compliance burden squarely on participants following a breach, imposing significant costs associated with rectifying vulnerabilities and ensuring adherence to security standards post facto. In the absence of proactive frameworks like ABDM, network participants would typically face the full financial ramifications of compliance with ISO 27001 standards and the additional expenses associated with obtaining licences from the UIDAI.

Under the ABDM framework, while the generation of ABHA IDs utilises Aadhaar, the integrated applications are subjected to Web Application Security Assessments (WASA) conducted by CERT-In empanelled agencies, thereby ensuring compliance is achieved proactively. Meanwhile, the National Health Authority (NHA) itself is held to the rigorous

standards of ISO 27001, alongside compliance obligations derived from its interactions with UIDAI.

This Ex Ante or *A priori* regulatory approach, epitomised by the ABDM, not only optimises compliance costs but also enhances the overall resilience and security of the digital ecosystem. By shifting the compliance burden from application developers to central administrative bodies responsible for maintaining registries and gateways, the framework fosters a streamlined process that mitigates risks while promoting innovation.

The different minimum standards for entry to DPI ecosystems are listed in [Annexure 2](#).

- **Digital Supply Chain Security: Ensuring Resilience Through Compliance**

In the spirit of fostering robust cyber resilience across expansive digital ecosystems, India's DPIs and Open Networks extend security compliance obligations beyond immediate network participants to encompass their entire digital supply chains. By doing so, they establish a multi-layered approach to ensuring that every segment of the digital ecosystem, from foundational infrastructure to service providers, is fortified against increasingly sophisticated cyber threats.

In DPI ecosystems such as Aadhaar, UPI, and the ABDM, participants are not only responsible for maintaining their own security compliance but are also entrusted with ensuring that their technology service providers (TSPs) adhere to the stringent security obligations embedded within the ecosystem. This creates a cascading effect, whereby

the security resilience of the broader digital supply chain is strengthened through collective adherence to security standards. Such a policy decision to delegate security compliance responsibility to ecosystem participants for their respective TSPs is a key innovation in advancing cyber resilience across the larger digital landscape. Annexure 2 details the security compliance burdens for TSPs across DPI and Open Network ecosystems.

The importance of this approach becomes particularly evident in light of recent cyber intrusions targeting supply chains. Infiltration of digital supply chains through targeted cyberattacks is an ever-present threat. Malicious actors often exploit vulnerabilities within upstream dependencies—such as operating systems, middleware, or third-party applications—to gain entry into a more secure network. By imposing security compliance obligations across the entire supply chain, India's DPIs aim to create a hardened digital environment where each participant, and their affiliated service providers, contributes to the overall security of the network.

This emphasis on supply chain security is further enhanced through the use of compliance frameworks, such as Web Application Security Assessments (WASA), which are mandated for all network participants. By centralising critical security functions, DPIs significantly reduce the compliance burden on edge participants, allowing them to focus on building innovative consumer experiences while ensuring that core security responsibilities are rigorously upheld at the centre.

- Interweaving/building on top of other DPI to reduce security compliance burden on edge

Building on top of existing DPI can significantly reduce the security compliance burden at the edge. By interweaving with established DPIs, organisations can leverage already robust security frameworks, enhancing overall protection while minimising the need for redundant security implementations. For instance, Aadhaar's stringent security features are mandated for all its licence holders, thereby elevating the security threshold across the board. This approach not only strengthens security but also streamlines compliance efforts, making it easier for entities to adhere to high standards without duplicating efforts.

- Obfuscation of Identity

A key security feature offered by all the DPI and Open Networks under study (ABDM, UPI and Aadhaar) is the ability to obfuscate user identity in transactions. This feature is enabled through a variety of methods dependent upon the ecosystem. Broadly, two primary kinds of obfuscation solutions are offered by DPI and Open Network ecosystems, namely: Virtual Private Addresses (VPAs) and Virtual IDs (VIDs).

ABDM and UPI offer VPAs as a standard feature for ecosystem onboarded users. VPAs in the UPI context obfuscate sender and receiver banking details, sharing instead an address similar to an e-mail address. Users can generate multiple VPAs to be linked to the same or multiple accounts. Through VPAs, users are empowered to implement security by compartmentalisation vis-a-vis their digital payments experience. Through

compartmentalisation, users can ensure that in case of a breach of a certain VPA or transaction party, only specific transaction records are compromised, with the larger transaction history remaining relatively more secure.

In the ABDM ecosystem on the other hand, VPAs are used to share health records to specific Health Information Providers (HIPs: hospitals, health apps, labs etc.). Users can select specific records to be linked to specific VPAs and to be shared to specific HIPs. Akin to the UPI approach, VPAs in the ABDM ecosystem advance user-enabled security by compartmentalisation.

Unlike ID systems like the US' Social Security Number, under the Aadhaar ecosystem, users are empowered to generate VIDs to be shared with entities for authentication or e-kyc. VIDs mask the original Aadhaar number, ensuring that in the case of a breach, Aadhaar details are provided with additional safeguards.

- **Ecosystem wide monitoring & threat intelligence**

A key effect of federal architectures is the centralisation of security critical functions and ecosystem wide threat intelligence. All the DPI ecosystems under study sport central level cyber threat intelligence features enabled through Security Operations Centres. [Annexure 3](#) highlights the cyber threat and Security Operations Centres across diverse DPI and Open Network ecosystems.

DPI Types of Security Architectures

Despite sharing certain overarching common security characteristics, India's DPI ecosystems exhibit distinct security architectures.

1. **Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI):**

Aadhaar's Security Architecture

The UIDAI serves as the principal custodian of India's Aadhaar ecosystem. The security architecture underpinning Aadhaar is based upon compartmentalisation of responsibilities and security compliance of participants. UIDAI controls the Central Identity Repository (CIDR), access to which is only permitted for 1:1 matching for authentication and e-KYC.

Authentication User Agencies (AUAs) or Requesting Entities are entities wishing to leverage Aadhaar as an identifier for authentication and e-KYC. AUAs can be public or private entities and must show compliance with UIDAI's security standards and policies prior to entering the ecosystem. AUAs are also subject to annual security audits by UIDAI undertaken in partnership with the Standardisation Testing and Quality Certification Directorate (STQC) under the Indian Ministry of Electronics and IT. UIDAI sets the standards for audits.

At the core of UIDAI's regulatory regime is a robust set of compliance obligations, encompassing advanced encryption standards and multi-layered authentication

protocols. AUAs are required to uphold the highest levels of data protection, ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of sensitive information. To reinforce this, UIDAI conducts both third-party and internal audits of these entities, verifying that security protocols are meticulously observed and that any vulnerabilities are promptly addressed.

The Aadhaar security model revolves around compartmentalised access, with data encryption mechanisms and role-based authorizations forming key pillars of its defence strategy. Each access request within the ecosystem is monitored and controlled, ensuring that only authorised agencies can retrieve specific, necessary data. By enforcing strict limitations on data access, UIDAI effectively mitigates the risks associated with excessive data exposure, thereby reducing the likelihood of breaches.

Real-time monitoring is another cornerstone of UIDAI's approach. Through the deployment of a central Security Operations Centre (SOC), the ecosystem is continuously supervised for irregularities or potential intrusions. This real-time vigilance allows the system to identify and respond to threats promptly, enhancing the resilience of the Aadhaar infrastructure against evolving cyber threats.

Furthermore, UIDAI's focus on continuous compliance ensures that all actors within the ecosystem maintain a proactive stance on security. Regular audits, compliance reviews, and stringent adherence to UIDAI specified standards for information security create an environment where vulnerabilities are systematically identified and rectified. This dynamic, multi-tiered security architecture is not only designed to defend against

external threats but also fosters internal accountability, ensuring that the highest standards of data protection are maintained across the Aadhaar ecosystem.

2. The Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission (ABDM): A Federated Approach to Healthcare Data Security

The Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission (ABDM) exemplifies DPI's health ecosystem, linking providers, patients, and regulators through a federated architecture. Healthcare providers—hospitals, labs—join voluntarily, adopting interoperable standards (e.g., Health Facility Registry) to access a national network (NHA, n.d.). Data remains decentralized, stored at provider edges, not a central repository, reducing breach risks like SingHealth's 1.5 million record leak. Consent drives sharing: patients control access via tools like the ABHA number, a unique identifier.

Centralized components, such as ABDM's registry and monitoring systems, anchor this model with fortified security, adhering to ISO 27001 standards (NHA, 2023). This global benchmark mandates encryption, access controls, and regular audits, ensuring resilience at scale (ISO/IEC 27001:2013). A Security Operation Center (SOC) oversees transactions, flagging anomalies in real-time—e.g., 100 million sandbox transactions tested this. This fortified core complements federated edges, where voluntary providers adopt protocols to participate, aligning with DPI's market-driven ethos.

ABDM's design mitigates centralized vulnerabilities while leveraging network effects: providers outside the ecosystem lose interoperability, a pressure reinforced by DPDP's data protection mandates (2023). Its hybrid approach—federated edges, fortified

cores—offers a scalable blueprint, though its efficacy awaits broader adoption and testing.

DPI Cases and Breaches

CASE I: HEALTH SECTOR; SingHealth (Singapore) and ABDM

The SingHealth Breach

One of the most devastating (and possibly state sponsored) cyber attacks in the health sector was the 2018 breach of the Singapore Health Services Private Limited (“SingHealth”), the largest healthcare cluster in the public healthcare sector of Singapore. Through the attack the Prime Minister of Singapore’s Personally Identifiable Information (PII) and Personal Health Information (PHI) “was specifically targeted and repeatedly accessed”,²⁷ and the personal data of over 1.5 million patients was compromised, including: names, NRIC numbers, addresses, genders, races, dates of birth, clinical prescriptions of over 150,000 patients.

The attacker bore the distinguishing features of an Advanced Persistent Threat group, with the unambiguous objective being the personal and outpatient medication data of the Prime Minister in the main, and also that of other patients.

²⁷Committee of Inquiry, Government of Singapore. (2019). *Public report of the Committee of Inquiry into the cyber attack on Singapore Health Services Private Limited (SingHealth) in 2018*. Government of Singapore. <https://file.go.gov.sg/singhealthcoi.pdf>

The investigation into the cyberattack revealed significant shortcomings in the system's security posture and Information Security management system. In particular, weaknesses were observed in cybersecurity awareness, training, and incident response among key personnel. Significant known vulnerabilities remained unmitigated, poor operational security implemented. while the centralised architecture exacerbated the extent of the attacker's exploits, enabling the attacker to query to and retrieve data from the SCM database.

Additionally, lack of an effective two-factor authentication (2FA) processes for exchanging health data eased the attacker's path. The attack was also exacerbated by a series of vulnerabilities in the network, including weak authentication methods, inadequate network segregation, and coding flaws in the SCM system. These weaknesses allowed the attacker to exploit the system over a period of months, using stealthy techniques to exfiltrate sensitive data.

The findings also noted a dearth of cyber threat intelligence within the organisation, compounded by delayed incident reporting and ineffective internal communication, all of which conspired to facilitate the exfiltration of patient data.

ABDM's Security Model: Preventing Similar Breaches

Had SingHealth been integrated into India's ABDM ecosystem, many of the vulnerabilities that enabled the 2018 breach could have been mitigated, if not entirely prevented. The ABDM framework institutes a federated digital health architecture that decentralises data storage and access, reducing reliance on a single point of failure. Under such a model, sensitive data is not housed in a centralised database, thereby

compartmentalising risk and limiting the potential for large-scale breaches like that experienced by SingHealth. In particular, we estimate that 14 out of 17 findings identified by the Parliamentary Committee report could have been prevented (details in Annexure).

Furthermore, in an ABDM-integrated system, SingHealth would have benefited from the oversight of a centralised Security Operations Centre (SOC). This SOC would have provided continuous monitoring and real-time threat intelligence, allowing for the early detection of the attacker's tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs). The Singaporean Parliamentary Report itself concluded that a dedicated SOC could have significantly helped to “improve the ability to detect and respond to intrusions.”

Another critical feature of the ABDM model is its compliance-by-design approach and common ecosystem-wide security policies, rooted in international cybersecurity standards, including ISO27001. In this hypothetical scenario, SingHealth would have been subject to stringent reporting and training requirements, with mandatory Web Application Security Assessments (WASA) ensuring that security protocols were rigorously enforced. As identified by the Parliamentary Committee Report, the lack of such obligations in the SingHealth case contributed to delayed responses, as key personnel were unfamiliar with incident reporting procedures and the importance of escalating security concerns in a timely manner.

The ABDM ecosystem also mandates a robust consent management framework, functioning as a second factor for authentication. According to the Singaporean Parliamentary Report, the absence of such a mechanism in the SingHealth breach

allowed the attacker to bypass security protocols with relative ease. In contrast, under ABDM, each health data transaction would have required explicit patient consent, adding an additional layer of protection against unauthorised access. Furthermore, the federated architecture would have ensured that even if one segment of the system were compromised, the attacker would be unable to access the entirety of the patient data.

The ABDM framework also integrates regular audits of system code and software vulnerabilities, addressing many of the technical deficiencies that allowed the attacker to move laterally across SingHealth's network. This includes token-based access control, periodic source code audits, and enhanced network segregation—all of which would have reduced the attack surface and limited the effectiveness of any breach attempt.

The SingHealth breach exemplifies the vulnerabilities that arise from inadequate cybersecurity practices and reliance on centralised data architectures. However, had the organisation operated within the confines of the ABDM model, many of the security weaknesses that facilitated the attack could have been identified and addressed preemptively. Through its federated architecture, continuous monitoring, and stringent compliance requirements, ABDM offers a robust defence against sophisticated cyber threats, demonstrating the critical role that DPI can play in safeguarding sensitive health information. While no system is impervious to an Advanced Persistent Threat, the ABDM model would have significantly reduced the scale and impact of the breach, underscoring the importance of robust security frameworks in an increasingly digitised world.

CASE II: HEALTH SECTOR; MediSecure (Australia) and ABDM

The MediSecure Incident

The 2024 ransomware attack on and data breach of Australia's MediSecure marked a watershed moment in the discourse surrounding security of national digital health systems. MediSecure was until late 2023, a constituent in the duopoly of prescription delivery services serving patients nation-wide in Australia.²⁸ The ransomware attack, which resulted in the exfiltration of over 6.5 terabytes of data²⁹, compromised the personal information of an estimated 12.9 million patients who had utilised MediSecure's services between March 2019 and November 2023³⁰.

The breached data points were comprehensive, encompassing sensitive and highly personal information. This included full names, titles, dates of birth, gender, email addresses, physical addresses, phone numbers, and unique individual healthcare identifiers (IHI). In addition, critical identification details such as Medicare card numbers, including individual identifiers and expiration dates, were compromised. Other sensitive data involved concession and veterans' card numbers, prescription medication

²⁸ Australian Government Department of Home Affairs. (n.d.). *MediSecure cyber security incident*. Home Affairs Cyber Security. <https://www.homeaffairs.gov.au/about-us/our-portfolios/cyber-security/cyber-coordinator/medisecure-cyber-security-incident>

²⁹ MediSecure Notification. (n.d.). MediSecure Notification Blog. WordPress. <https://medisecurenotification.wordpress.com/>

³⁰ Australian Government Department of Home Affairs. (n.d.). *MediSecure cyber security incident*. Home Affairs Cyber Security. <https://www.homeaffairs.gov.au/cyber-security-subsite/Pages/nat-cyber-security-coordinator/medisecure-cyber-security-incident.aspx>

details—encompassing drug names, strength, dosage, quantity, and instructions—as well as the medical reasons for the prescriptions.³¹

MediSecure refrained from disclosing the precise cause of the breach, though their public statement alluded to early indicators suggesting that the incident "originated from one of [their] third-party vendors."³² This admission reveals an underlying vulnerability endemic to systems reliant on external intermediaries—a vulnerability that this breach so grievously exposed.

ABDM's Security Model: Preventing Similar Breaches

The vulnerabilities inherent in MediSecure's architectural model underscore the systemic risks posed by centralised prescription delivery systems reliant on third-party intermediaries. ABDM, by contrast, presents a more resilient model, one that could have mitigated many of the risks exposed in the MediSecure breach. At the core of ABDM's architecture is the elimination of intermediaries like MediSecure. Rather than relying on external agents for prescription delivery, ABDM facilitates direct, bilateral, consent-based and secure transactions between healthcare service providers and pharmacies within the ecosystem. This peer-to-peer (P2P) approach, executed via open protocols, decentralises data storage and diminishes the risks associated with single points of failure, such as those MediSecure faced.

While MediSecure indicated that the breached data had been encrypted, the quality and strength of the encryption protocols remain unclear, thereby leaving victims susceptible

³¹ MediSecure Notification. (n.d.). MediSecure Notification Blog. WordPress. <https://medisecurenotification.wordpress.com/>

³² MediSecure Notification. (n.d.). MediSecure Notification Blog. WordPress. <https://medisecurenotification.wordpress.com/>

to decryption attempts. In contrast, ABDM enforces a uniform encryption standard across its ecosystem, ensuring that in the unlikely event of a breach, victims would be assured that their data remains protected by robust and advanced encryption measures. This standardised encryption protocol not only strengthens data security but also builds trust among users that their personal and health information cannot be easily compromised.

The MediSecure breach, which allegedly originated from the compromise of a third-party vendor, further underscores the risks associated with outsourcing critical functions to external partners. In a hypothetical scenario where MediSecure operated under ABDM's integrated framework, the company would have borne responsibility for ensuring that all third-party vendors adhered to ABDM's stringent security standards. This compliance obligation would have introduced a heightened level of oversight and scrutiny, effectively limiting the vulnerabilities posed by external partners. By imposing strict third-party compliance requirements, ABDM reduces the likelihood of such breaches occurring through intermediary weaknesses.

CASE III: IDENTITY - RENAPER (Argentina) and Aadhaar³³

The RENAPER Breach

In one of the most consequential breaches of recent times, Argentina's National Registry of Persons (RENAPER) was compromised, leading to an egregious exposure

³³Lok Sabha, Government of India. (n.d.). *Unstarred Question No. 3432: [USE OF E-KYC AUTHENTICATION SERVICES]*. Parliament of India.
<https://sansad.in/getFile/loksabhaquestions/annex/1712/AU3432.pdf?source=pqals>

of PII for millions of Argentine citizens³⁴. This breach, which surfaced publicly in 2021, underscored both the vulnerabilities inherent in centralised data systems and the profound risks posed by improper access controls and oversight failures.

The attacker, operating under a veil of anonymity, initially targeted high-profile individuals—celebrities and public figures including renowned footballers Lionel Messi and Sergio Agüero—leaking their personal data via the social media platform Twitter³⁵. This act, while dramatic in its public display, was merely a precursor to a far graver revelation: the entirety of Argentina’s national database had been compromised, with sensitive details of over 45 million citizens subsequently offered on dark web forums for sale.

The scope of the breach was staggering. Data encompassing citizens' full names, national identification numbers, addresses, dates of birth, and even ID card photographs was laid bare, leaving millions vulnerable to identity theft, financial fraud, and further exploitation by malicious actors.

An investigation revealed that the system’s security vulnerabilities, including improper access controls, lack of strong authentication mechanisms, and insufficient oversight of user activity, played a critical role in enabling the breach. The absence of real-time

³⁴ Gobierno de Argentina. (n.d.). *El RENAPER detectó el uso indebido de una clave otorgada a un organismo público y formalizó la denuncia*. Argentina.gob.ar. <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/noticias/el-renaper-detecto-el-uso-indebido-de-una-clave-otorgada-un-organismo-publico-y-formalizo>

³⁵The Record. (2021, October 13). *Hacker steals government ID database for Argentina’s entire population*. The Record by Recorded Future. <https://therecord.media/hacker-steals-government-id-database-for-argentinas-entire-population>

monitoring and effective internal checks allowed the hacker to exfiltrate data undetected, leaving the entire population at risk.

Aadhaar's Security Model: Preventing Similar Breaches

Had the RENAPER system been structured along the stringent lines of India's Aadhaar architecture, the outcome might have been starkly different. The Aadhaar framework is underpinned by multi-factor authentication (MFA) protocols that require multiple layers of verification—biometrics, demographic data, and one-time passwords (OTPs)—before access to sensitive information is granted. This stands in stark contrast to RENAPER's compromised access point, where a single VPN breach provided entry into the entire database.

Another critical feature that differentiates Aadhaar is its role-based access controls. In the Aadhaar ecosystem, entities such as Authentication User Agencies (AUAs) and Authentication Service Agencies (ASAs) are granted only the minimal necessary access to fulfil their operational mandates³⁶, ensuring that access to data is tightly controlled and subject to continuous monitoring.

In an Aadhaar-modelled RENAPER system, the onboarding of AUAs and ASAs would be meticulously governed by stringent security compliance conditions, ensuring that only those entities demonstrating sufficient cyber resilience are granted the privilege to authenticate or perform electronic Know Your Customer (e-KYC) processes. These

³⁶Unique Identification Authority of India. (n.d.). *Operation model – Authentication ecosystem*. UIDAI. <https://uidai.gov.in/en/ecosystem/authentication-ecosystem/operation-model.html>

onboarding regulations, which apply equally to both private enterprises and government bodies, would enforce comprehensive cybersecurity standards as a prerequisite to system integration.

In such a hypothetical adaptation, the Argentine Ministry of Health would be obligated to adhere to Requesting Entity V3 (RE Checklist V3) like checklist³⁷, a standard designed to ensure robust security practices. This mandatory compliance, enforced at the point of onboarding, would encompass a broad array of operational security requirements. In this scenario, the Ministry of Health's internal security controls would have been rigorously fortified under these stringent requirements, thus significantly reducing the likelihood of the breach that ultimately compromised the entire RENAPER database. Such anticipatory measures, emblematic of Aadhaar's model, would have instilled an enhanced layer of security resilience, effectively mitigating potential vulnerabilities before they could be exploited.

Additionally, the robust encryption protocols employed by Aadhaar ensure that data remains secure both in transmission and at rest. Even in the unlikely event of unauthorised access, any compromised data would remain indecipherable without the appropriate decryption keys. This is a far cry from the situation with RENAPER, where lax or nonexistent encryption practices meant that the compromised data was immediately exploitable by the attacker, placing millions of citizens at risk.

Moreover, every transaction and query is logged and subject to audit, thereby preventing unauthorised or excessive access to the system. Had RENAPER adopted

³⁷Unique Identification Authority of India. (n.d.). Requesting entity compliance checklist (Version 3.0). UIDAI. https://uidai.gov.in/images/resource/Requesting_Entity_Compliance_Checklist_V3.0.pdf

such rigorous controls, the anomalous data access patterns would have been swiftly detected, and the breach likely prevented or mitigated.

Moreover, Aadhaar's threat intelligence and real-time monitoring systems may have detected suspicious activity much earlier. Aadhaar's operations are continuously monitored by UIDAI's SOC that tracks all authentication requests and system activities. In the RENAPER case, the misuse of VPN credentials went unnoticed for an extended period, but in the Aadhaar ecosystem, such anomalies would trigger immediate alerts, limiting the scope of any potential breach.

Additionally, the strong encryption protocols used in Aadhaar ensure that even if one part of the system is breached, the data remains unreadable and unusable without the appropriate decryption keys.

CASE IV: IDENTITY - Social Security-National Public Data (United States of America) and Aadhaar

The National Public Data Breach

National Public Data (NPD) is a US-based private data aggregator or data broker which aggregates data in order to run background checks³⁸. NPD had a massive database stolen, a database containing 2.9 billion rows of private records. Among those private records are the social security numbers of millions of Americans. The cybercriminal

³⁸National Public Data. (n.d.). About us. National Public Data.
<https://nationalpublicdata.com/about-us.html>

group USDoD claimed responsibility for the incident and listed the database for sale on an underworld forum on the dark web, with an asking price of \$3.5 million.³⁹⁴⁰

A report by the Office of US Congressman Torres estimates that up to 85.1% of US Congress members had their personal data leaked through the breach. In particular, the breach impacts up to 84.5% of US Representatives and up to 87.9% of US Senators.⁴¹

Specific data points breached included names, email addresses, phone numbers, mailing addresses, dates-of-birth and most concerning, full Social Security Numbers (SSNs: the US's national identification number)⁴².

The Dilemma of Social Security Numbers

The breach sheds light on a fundamental dilemma within the SSN ecosystem: while SSNs are indispensable for identity verification across myriad societal and commercial domains, they simultaneously represent a significant security risk. The Identity Theft Resource Center ranked SSNs as the second most breached data attribute in 2022, with even partial SSNs appearing among the top 30 breached data points.⁴³

³⁹ Comer, J., & Mace, N. (2024, August 22). *Letter to Mr. Salvatore Verini regarding National Public Data breach*. U.S. House Committee on Oversight and Accountability.

<https://oversight.house.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/NPD-Breach-Letter-08222024.pdf>

⁴⁰ *Burgen v. Jerico Pictures, Inc., No. 0:24-cv-61384 (S.D. Fla. 2024)*. Retrieved from https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf

⁴¹ **Torres, R. (2024)**. *An investigative report on the National Public Data breach*. Office of Congressman Ritchie Torres. Retrieved from <https://d12t4t5x3vyizu.cloudfront.net/ritchietorres.house.gov/uploads/2024/09/C4FF5BA1-1BBF-464B-AB-DB-783E649A5482.pdf>

⁴² National Public Data. (n.d.). *Breach information*. National Public Data. <https://nationalpublicdata.com/Breach.html>

⁴³ https://www.idtheftcenter.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/ITRC_2022-Data-Breach-Report_Final.pdf

The Social Security Administration (SSA) itself acknowledges that once an individual's SSN is compromised, "the potential for a thief to illegitimately gain access to bank accounts, credit cards, driving records, tax and employment histories and other private information increases."⁴⁴⁴⁵ Courts have accordingly referred to SSNs as the "gold standard" for identity theft, and "the most dangerous type of personal information in the hands of identity thieves."⁴⁴⁶

Nevertheless, the pervasive use of SSNs as a primary identifier renders their exclusion from modern transactions virtually impossible. Initially conceived as a means for tracking earnings and administering retirement benefits for the federal Social Security system⁴⁷⁴⁸, SSNs have evolved into a de facto **unique numeric identifier**⁴⁹⁵⁰, ubiquitously relied upon for identity verification⁵¹ in both the public and private sectors, leading the State of California to call them "the key to a lot of your [users'] personal

⁴⁴Social Security Administration. (n.d.). *Protecting your Social Security Number (SSN)*. U.S. Social Security Administration. <https://www.ssa.gov/phila/ProtectingSSNs.htm>

⁴⁵ [Burgen v. Jerico Pictures, Inc., No. 0:24-cv-61384 \(S.D. Fla. 2024\)](https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf). Retrieved from https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf

⁴⁶ [Burgen v. Jerico Pictures, Inc., No. 0:24-cv-61384 \(S.D. Fla. 2024\)](https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf). Retrieved from https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf

⁴⁷ California Office of the Attorney General. (n.d.). Your Social Security number is the key. California Department of Justice. Retrieved February 15, 2025, from <https://oag.ca.gov/idtheft/facts/your-ssn>

⁴⁸ N.C. Gen. Stat. § 132-1.10(1) cited in [Burgen v. Jerico Pictures, Inc., No. 0:24-cv-61384 \(S.D. Fla. 2024\)](https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf). Retrieved from https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf

⁴⁹Social Security Administration. (n.d.). *Protecting your Social Security Number (SSN)*. U.S. Social Security Administration. <https://www.ssa.gov/phila/ProtectingSSNs.htm>

⁵⁰ [Burgen v. Jerico Pictures, Inc., No. 0:24-cv-61384 \(S.D. Fla. 2024\)](https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf). Retrieved from https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf

⁵¹ N.C. Gen. Stat. § 132-1.10(1) cited in [Burgen v. Jerico Pictures, Inc., No. 0:24-cv-61384 \(S.D. Fla. 2024\)](https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf). Retrieved from https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf

information.”⁵² The NPD breach thus underscores the inherent risks of relying on a singular, highly sensitive identifier without adequate safeguards.

Aadhaar’s Security Model: Preventing Similar Breaches

Had the SSN system been architected on similar lines to India’s Aadhaar ecosystem, the outcome might have been starkly different. SSNs hold a unique place in US society, where sharing them is both risky and essential. Au contraire, users under the UIDAI ecosystem are empowered to obfuscation through at-will generation of Virtual Identities (VIDs) and masked versions of Aadhaar by users to be used for authentication in place of a full Aadhaar number or a copy of an unmasked Aadhaar. VIDs are “temporary, revocable 16-digit random number[s] mapped with the Aadhaar number[s]” which is usable “in lieu of Aadhaar number whenever authentication or e-KYC services are performed” and cannot be used to derive the Aadhaar number.⁵³

Masked Aadhaar on the other hand “replaces the first 8 digits of the Aadhaar number with “xxxx-xxxx” while only the last 4 digits of the Aadhaar Number are visible.”

Obfuscation of Aadhaar number and the temporary nature of VIDs disincentives organisations from storing VIDs.⁵⁴ Enabling similar obfuscation methods by the SSA would have limited the extent to which full SSNs would need to be shared with third parties for authentication. In particular, implementing obfuscation methods would have

⁵² [California Office of the Attorney General. \(n.d.\). Your Social Security number is the key. California Department of Justice. Retrieved February 15, 2025, from https://oag.ca.gov/idtheft/facts/your-ssn](https://oag.ca.gov/idtheft/facts/your-ssn)

⁵³ Unique Identification Authority of India. (n.d.). *Virtual ID (VID) – Aadhaar online services FAQs*. UIDAI. <https://uidai.gov.in/en/284-faqs/aadhaar-online-services/virtual-id-vid.html>

⁵⁴ Unique Identification Authority of India. (n.d.). *Virtual ID (VID) – Aadhaar online services FAQs*. UIDAI. <https://uidai.gov.in/en/284-faqs/aadhaar-online-services/virtual-id-vid.html>

limited the number of SSN numbers NPD had stored in their databases, thereby restricting the magnitude of the breach's impact.

A class-action lawsuit filed by the victims of the breach alleges that NPD "did not use reasonable security procedures and practices appropriate to the nature of the sensitive information....such as encrypting the information or deleting it when it is no longer needed." In particular, the suit alleges that NPD did not adhere to the security guidelines issued by the US Federal Bureau of Investigation and the US Federal Trade Commission.⁵⁵

The FTC's guidance is remarkably similar to the prescribed security standards set by UIDAI. [Annexure 5](#) highlights the overlaps between the two. All 6 of the points in FTC's guidelines identified by victims in the breach in their class action suit as relevant to the case are addressed by incorporating UIDAI-style features.

A key point in the FTC's guidelines identified by victims in the breach in their class action suit as relevant to the case was securely disposing and/or encrypting PII. UIDAI's RE Checklist V3 obligates Requesting Entities (REs) to define procedures for disposal of information assets and to ensure that Aadhaar number or even the VID is not stored by device operators or at the AUA's servers. While permitted to store Aadhaar numbers, REs must ensure that Aadhaar data is stored only in a separate secure and encrypted database/vault/system termed as "Aadhaar Data Vault," the keys to which must be secured in a separate Hardware Security Module (HSM).

⁵⁵ [Burgen v. Jerico Pictures, Inc., No. 0:24-cv-61384 \(S.D. Fla. 2024\)](https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf). Retrieved from https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf

REs must map Aadhaar numbers to separate reference identifiers and only use reference identifiers instead for operational purposes. The mapping of Aadhaar numbers and reference identifiers is also to be stored in the Aadhaar Data Vault. Additionally, any demographic, biometric or e-kyc captured by RE must be encrypted immediately.

Implementation of aforementioned controls in the SSN ecosystem would have ensured uniform standards for PII erasure and encryption amongst all entities seeking to leverage SSN. In the hypothetical scenario where such strategies, especially regarding encryption and the Data Vault, were implemented by the SSA, the cybercriminal USDoD would have faced significantly greater resistance in attempts to access or find value in encrypted SSN data exfiltrated in the NPD breach.

The plaintiffs in the class action suit also highlighted the relevance of FTC's guidelines stressing businesses understand their network's vulnerabilities. UIDAI's RE Checklist V3 obligates REs to perform source code review of the modules and applications used for Authentication and e-KYC. REs must undergo audits by a certified auditor which must include vulnerability assessment and penetration testing on networks, infrastructure and applications. REs must institute annual standard certification and audit processes for applications, devices and networks. Annual reviews and assessments of REs must be undertaken by CERT-in empanelled agencies. REs are also obligated to perform periodic information security risk assessments on its third parties with access to Aadhaar data.

In the hypothetical scenario where the SSA had instituted similar network security obligations for leveraging SSNs, the USDoD group's ability to breach NPD's defences to access SSN and other PII would be severely restricted. Through hardening and audit mechanisms, NPD's defences, akin to the defences of all other ecosystems participants in this hypothetical, would conform to best practices and guidelines through the mere act of participating in the ecosystem.

With an Aadhaar-like regime for SSN, compliance with aforementioned controls would not need to be tested only when a breach occurs and victims approach courts where NPD must now demonstrate compliance. A key feature of the UIDAI ecosystem is that entities seeking to leverage Aadhaar as an identifier are required to demonstrate Ex-Ante or *A priori* compliance with prescribed security standards prior to being permitted to engage in authentication or e-KYC transactions. Therefore, NPD would have necessarily needed to implement mandated controls even before requesting to use Aadhaar as an identifier.

In conclusion, an Aadhaar-like regime for the U.S. SSN system would have fundamentally transformed the security landscape, enforcing stringent compliance mechanisms, promoting data obfuscation, and requiring ex-ante adherence to robust security protocols. Through these measures, the systemic vulnerabilities exposed by the NPD breach could have been mitigated, offering valuable lessons for enhancing the security of national identity systems in the digital age.

Conclusion

India's DPI offers a voluntary, ex-ante cybersecurity model, distinct from mandatory regimes. Network effects drive compliance: entities join ecosystems (e.g., Aadhaar, UPI), adopting standards to avoid exclusion—a pressure aligned with DPDP, 2023. Federated architectures (ABDM), obfuscation (VIDs), and interoperability outperform centralized systems (e.g., SingHealth, SSN), mitigating breach risks via design. Centralized hubs, secured to ISO 27001, balance this, distinguishing DPI's resilience.

External leaks—like Resecurity's 2023 incident (815 million records via physical cards)—reveal limits: non-licensed entities expose gaps, yet this nudges them into DPI's fold, a market-driven safeguard. User tools (VIDs) enhance security, though optional uptake signals a sociotechnical frontier. This hybrid resilience—voluntary compliance at scale, fortified by standards—positions DPI as a scalable alternative for nations balancing sovereignty and security.

This paper outlines DPI's framework, not its definitive success—breach resistance, adoption rates, and DPDP's interplay await empirical scrutiny. It invites researchers to test its promise against real-world challenges, offering a blueprint for voluntary governance in a cyber-threatened age.

Towards a Global DPI Security Research Agenda: This paper outlines DPI's framework as a conceptual foundation, not a final verdict. Its promise—breach resistance, adoption dynamics, and synergy with ISO 27001 or DPDP—demands global scrutiny. Can voluntary ecosystems deter non-compliance at scale? How do fortified

cores balance cost and security? Researchers must test DPI's blueprint across contexts, shaping a new frontier for cybersecurity governance.

Annexures

Annexure 1a:

Annexure 1b: Security Provisions Comparison:

NDHM vs PDP Bill 2019

Provision/Area	NDHM Health Data Policy	PDP Bill, 2019 (Section references)	Similarity Rating
General Security Obligation	Requires data fiduciaries and processors to implement organizational and technical safeguards appropriate to the nature of data processed.	Section 24(1) mandates necessary security safeguards , including de-identification and encryption.	✓✓ (Very High)
Data Minimization	Collection/processing limited to what is necessary (Clause 7).	Section 6 – same wording: "only to the extent necessary."	✓✓

De-identification & Anonymisation	Defined and required for certain processing purposes (Clause 4(g), (j), (bb), etc.)	Section 3(2), 3(16), 3(34) – similar definitions and emphasis.	✓✓
Pseudonymisation	Defined and recommended for risk minimization (Clause 4(cc))	Not explicitly used but implied through anonymisation/de-identification.	✓ (Moderate)
Security by Design	“Security and Privacy by Design” is a guiding principle of NDHM (Clause 1).	Section 22 mandates a Privacy by Design Policy for fiduciaries.	✓✓
Regular Audits	Clause 6 outlines a governance structure including DPO, and mentions audit mechanisms.	Sections 29 and 30 require periodic audits and DPO appointment.	✓✓

Data Breach Management	Not specified in great detail, implied under security responsibilities and grievance handling.	Section 25 – explicit breach notification to DPA and possibly data principals.	✓ (Partial)
Retention & Storage Limitation	Personal data retained only as long as necessary (Clause 14.1).	Section 9 mandates limited retention and periodic review.	✓✓
Processor Obligations	Processors must comply with the instructions of fiduciaries; no separate duties articulated.	Section 24 applies to processors too; shared responsibility.	✓ (Moderate)
Encryption / Technical Standards	Requires adherence to national/international standards for integrity and confidentiality.	Section 24(1)(a) mandates encryption and de-identification methods.	✓✓

Annexure 2: Security Compliances for Onboarding Across Different DPI/Open Network Ecosystems

DPI	ABDM	Aadhaar
Security Requirement for Onboarding	Yes	Yes
Security Compliance for Onboarding	Web Application Security Assessment from CERT-In Empanelled Agency (Source: Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission.)	UIDAI Standards for Requesting Entity Compliance covering: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Information to Aadhaar No. Holder 2. Security of the Authentication Devices and Applications 3. Network, systems, key management and data vault requirements 4. Security Framework Policy for Requesting Entities

	<p>(n.d.). <i>Sandbox exit documentation.</i> National Health Authority, Government of India. Retrieved February 15, 2025, from https://sandbox.abdm.gov.in/sandbox/v3/new-documentation?doc=SandboxExit)</p>	<p>5. Compliance Requirements</p> <p>6. Compliance to UIDAI Information Security Policy for AUA/KUA (Source: Unique Identification Authority of India. (n.d.). Requesting entity compliance checklist (Version 3.0). UIDAI. https://uidai.gov.in/images/resource/Requesting_Entity_Compliance_Checklist_V3.0.pdf)</p>
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Annexure 3: Security Obligations for Technology Service Providers Across Different DPI/Open Network Ecosystems

DPI/Open Network	ABDM	UPI	Aadhaar
Security Obligations for Technology Service Providers	<p>With Network Participant</p> <p>(Source: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. (n.d.). <i>Health data management policy.</i> Ayushman Bharat Digital</p>	<p>With Network Participant</p> <p>(Source: National Payments Corporation of India. (n.d.). <i>UPI roles & responsibilities.</i> Retrieved February 15, 2025, from https://www.npci.org.in/what-we-do/upi/roles-re</p>	<p>With Network Participant</p> <p>(Source: Comptroller and Auditor General of India. (2021). <i>Audit Report No. 24: Functioning of Unique Identification Authority of India (UIDAI) - Security of Aadhaar Information System.</i></p>

	Mission. Retrieved February 15, 2025, from https://abdm.gov.in:8081/uploads/health_data_management_policy_455613409c.pdf)	sponsibilities)	Retrieved February 15, 2025, from https://cag.gov.in/uploads/download_audit_report/2021/chap_5-0624d8136df3044.27838471.pdf)
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Annexure 4: Centralised Cyber Threat Intelligence Systems Across Different DPI/Open Network Ecosystems

DPI/Open Network	ABDM	Aadhaar
Central Threat Intelligence	Yes (Source: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. (n.d.).	Yes

Systems in Place	<p><i>Final report on National Digital Health Blueprint (NDHB).</i></p> <p>Retrieved February 15, 2025, from</p> <p>https://mohfw.gov.in/?q=newshighlights/final-report-national-digital-health-blueprint-ndhb)</p>	
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Annexure 5: SingHealth Parliamentary Committee Findings Mapped with ABDM Protections

Key Finding #1: IHiS staff did not have adequate levels of cybersecurity awareness, training, and resources to appreciate the security implications of their findings and to respond effectively to the attack

No.	Findings of the Committee Report	Protections in Hypothetical ABDM Integration
1.	A number of IHiS' IT administrators could not fully appreciate the security implications of their findings, and	Through the Security Operations Centre, the ABDM ecosystem is constantly monitored by threat analysts with the sole purpose of

	<p>were unable to co-relate these findings with the tactics, techniques, and procedures (“TTPs”) of an advanced cyber attacker.</p>	<p>detecting TTPs.</p>
<p>2.</p>	<p>They were also not familiar with the relevant IT security policy documents and the need to escalate the matter to CSA. There was also no incident reporting framework in place for the IT administrators.</p>	<p>Incident Reporting mandate in HDMP(33.2) for Network Participant. (Source: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. (n.d.). Health data management policy. Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission. Retrieved February 15, 2025, from https://abdm.gov.in:8081/uploads/health_data_management_policy_455613409c.pdf)</p> <p>As part of its ISO 27001 certification, NHA mandates ongoing training to ensure employees are familiar with relevant IT security policies.</p>

3.	Members of the Security Management Department, Computer Emergency Response Team, and senior members of IHiS' management were similarly unable to fully appreciate the security implications of the findings.	As part of its ISO 27001 certification and UIDAI Regulation 14.1(H), NHA mandates ongoing training to ensure employees are familiar with relevant IT security policies. Further, the NHA SOC is focused on correlating events to draw larger security implications.
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Key Finding #2: Certain IHiS staff holding key roles in IT security incident response and reporting failed to take appropriate, effective, or timely action, resulting in missed opportunities to prevent the stealing and exfiltrating of data in the attack

No	Findings of the Committee Report	Protections in Hypothetical ABDM Integration
1.	The Security Incident Response Manager ("SIRM") and Cluster Information Security	NHA, the implementing body of ABDM, has a

	<p>Officer (“Cluster ISO”) for SingHealth, who were responsible for incident response and reporting, held mistaken understandings of what constituted a ‘security incident’, and when a security incident should be reported.</p>	<p>Security Operations Centre (SOC). SOC is also envisioned in the foundation documents of the National Digital Health Mission (ABDM). As the parliamentary report itself notes, a SoC would have helped to “improve the ability to detect and respond to intrusions.”</p>
2.	<p>The SIRM delayed reporting because he felt that additional pressure would be put on him and his team once the situation became known to management..</p>	<p>No Effect</p>
3.	<p>The evidence also suggests that the reluctance to escalate the matter may have come from a belief that it would not reflect well in the eyes of the organisation if the matter turned out to be a false alarm</p>	<p>No Effect</p>

4.	The Cluster ISO did not understand the significance of the information provided to him, and did not take any steps to better understand the information. Instead, he effectively abdicated to the SIRM the responsibility of deciding whether to escalate the incident.	No Effect
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Key Finding #3: There were a number of vulnerabilities, weaknesses, and misconfigurations in the SingHealth network and SCM system that contributed to the attacker’s success in obtaining and exfiltrating the data, many of which could have been remedied before the attack

No	Findings of the Committee Report	Protections in Hypothetical ABDM Integration
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1.	<p>A significant vulnerability was the network connectivity between the SGH Citrix servers and the SCM database, which the attacker exploited to make queries to the database. The network connectivity was maintained for the use of administrative tools and custom applications, but there was no necessity to do so. The network connection was a critical pathway to the SCM database, over which the attacker was able to make SQL queries to and retrieve data from the SCM database.</p>	<p>Annual WASA:</p> <p>Conducted annually to ensure compliance and security within the system.</p> <p>Token Issuance:</p> <p>Access to ABDM systems is granted exclusively through issued auth token keys (JWT tokens).</p>
2.	<p>The SGH Citrix servers were not adequately secured against unauthorised access. Notably, the process requiring 2-factor authentication (“2FA”) for administrator access was not enforced as the exclusive means of logging in as an administrator. This allowed the attacker to access the server through other routes that did not require 2FA.</p>	<p>In ABDM, security is reinforced with two-factor authentication: JWT tokens for system access and a consent mechanism as a secondary check, reducing the risk of</p>

		unauthorised access.
3.	There was a coding vulnerability in the SCM application which was likely exploited by the attacker to obtain credentials for accessing the SCM database.	ISO27001, UIDAI RE Checklist V3 at central level mandate software security practices and source code audits WASA for Network Participants
4.	There were a number of other vulnerabilities in the network which were identified in a penetration test in early 2017, and which may have been exploited by the attacker. These included weak administrator account passwords and the need to improve network segregation for administrative access to critical servers such as the domain controller and the Citrix servers. Unfortunately, the remediation process undertaken by IHiS was mismanaged and inadequate, and a number of	ISO27001, UIDAI RE Checklist V3 at central level

	vulnerabilities remained at the time of the Cyber Attack.	
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Key Finding #4: The attacker was a skilled and sophisticated actor bearing the characteristics of an Advanced Persistent Threat group

No	Findings of the Committee Report	Protections in Hypothetical ABDM Integration
1.	The attacker had a clear goal in mind, namely the personal and outpatient medication data of the Prime Minister in the main, and also that of other patients.	NHA, the implementing body of ABDM, has a Security Operations Centre (SOC). SOC is also envisioned in the
2.	The attacker employed advanced TTPs, as seen from the suite of advanced, customised, and stealthy malware used, generally stealthy movements, and its ability to find and exploit various vulnerabilities in SingHealth’s IT network and the SCM application	foundation documents of the National Digital Health Mission (ABDM). As the parliamentary report itself notes, a SoC would have helped to
3.	The attacker was persistent, having established multiple footholds and backdoors,	“improve the ability to detect and respond to

	carried out its attack over a period of over 10 months, and made multiple attempts at accessing the SCM database using various methods.	intrusions.”
4.	The attacker was a well-resourced group, having an extensive command and control network, the capability to develop numerous customised tools, and a wide range of technical expertise.	

Key Finding #5: While our cyber defences will never be impregnable, and it may be difficult to prevent an Advanced Persistent Threat from breaching the perimeter of the network, the success of the attacker in obtaining and exfiltrating the data was not inevitable

No.	Findings of the Committee Report	Protections in Hypothetical ABDM Integration
1.	The attacker had a clear goal in mind, namely the personal and outpatient medication data of the	Security Operations Centre + federated

	Prime Minister in the main, and also that of other patients.	architecture (limits effect).
2.	The attacker employed advanced TTPs, as seen from the suite of advanced, customised, and stealthy malware used, generally stealthy movements, and its ability to find and exploit various vulnerabilities in SingHealth's IT network and the SCM application	

Annexure 5: The US FTC's Protecting Personal Information: A Guide for Business (PPI Guide)⁵⁶ and UIDAI's RE Checklist V3.⁵⁷

N O .	PPI Guide	RE Che cklis t Pt. No.	RE Checklist Point Description
1	Properly dispose of personal information that is no longer needed; maintain PII	6.26	The key(s) used for digitally signing of authentication request and decryption of e-KYC XML Response shall be stored in HSM only. The HSM used shall be FIPS i40

⁵⁶ **Federal Trade Commission.** (n.d.). *Protecting personal information: A guide for business.* Retrieved February 15, 2025, from

https://www.ftc.gov/system/files/documents/plain-language/pdf-0136_proteting-personal-information.pdf cited in *Burgen v. Jerico Pictures, Inc., No. 0:24-cv-61384 (S.D. Fla. 2024)*. Retrieved from https://www.classaction.org/media/burgen-v-jerico-pictures-inc_1.pdf

⁵⁷ Unique Identification Authority of India. (n.d.). Requesting entity compliance checklist (Version 3.0). UIDAI. https://uidai.gov.in/images/resource/Requesting_Entity_Compliance_Checklist_V3.0.pdf

	longer than is needed for authorization of a transaction		latest standard compliant. Requesting entity should comply with all the requirements of UIDAI circular K IJO2OI2O4I2OI7- UIDAI (Auth-I) dated 22 June 2017 (Implementation of HSM by Entity/ASA).
		6.27	Entity shall define a procedure for disposal of the information assets being used for authentication operations. Information systems/documents containing Aadhaar related information shall be disposed of securely
		6.30	Entity should ensure that the Aadhaar number/Virtual ID/ANCS Token provided by the resident for authentication request shall not be retained by the device operator or within the device or at the AUA server(s).
2	Encrypt information stored on computer networks;	3.7	Requesting entity (which is allowed to store Aadhaar number) and other entities are mandatorily required to collect and store Aadhaar number and any connected data on a separate secure database/vault/system termed as "Aadhaar Data Vault". This will be the only place where Aadhaar number and any connected data should be stored. Each Aadhaar number is to be referred by an additional key called as Reference key. Mapping of reference key and Aadhaar number is to be maintained in the Aadhaar Data Vault. The requesting entity should comply with all the requirements of the UIDAI circular K IIO2O/2O5/2O17-UIDAI (Auth-I) dated 25 July 2AI7 (Circular for Aadhaar Data Vault)
		2.4	After collecting necessary demographic and / or biometric information and/ or OTP from the Aadhaar number holder, the client application should immediately package and encr;prt these input parameters into PID block before any transmission, and should

			send it to the server of the requesting entity using secure protocols.
		2.5	AUA KUA should ensure PID Block is encrypted with a dynamic session key using AES 256 symmetric algorithm (AES/GcM/NoPadding) at the time of capture on the authentication device. Session key should be encrypted with a 2048-bit UIDAI public key using asymmetric algorithm (RSA/ECB/PKCS1 Padding). The entity should comply with API Specification (Latest) documents shared by authority from time to time.
		5.3	The requesting entity shall mask aadhaar numbers collected through physical forms or photocopies of Aadhaar letters by redacting the first 8 digits of the Aadhaar number before storing the physical copies.
3	Understand their network's vulnerabilities;	5.23	AUAs / KUAs shall ensure that its operations and systems are audited by an information systems auditor certified by a recognized body on an annual basis and on a need basis to ensure compliance with UIDAI standards and specifications. The audit report shall be shared with UIDAI upon request; If any non-compliance is found as a result of the audit, management shall: a) Determine the causes of the non-compliance; b) Evaluate the need for actions to avoid recurrence of the same; c) Determine and enforce the implementation of corrective and preventive action; d) Review the corrective action taken The entity should ensure to comply with Regulation Aadhaar (Data Security) Regulations, 2016.
		3.4	Entity should perform source code review of the modules and applications used for Authentication an4 e-KYC and undergo

			audit by a certified auditor and audit plan include organization information security policy inclusive of vulnerability assessment as well as penetration test on entity network, infrastructure and application
		4.6	Annual standard certification and audit process should be established for applications, devices, and overall networks across the ecosystem and also to ensure the compliance to standard security policy and procedure.
		4.10	The requesting entity shall ensure that it has provisions for annual reviews and assessments of its systems, infrastructure, etc., by a CERT-In empanelled agency to ensure compliance with Aadhaar Act, Regulations and specifications.
		6.34	Entity should implement process and procedures to perform periodic information security risk assessment on its third party having access to Aadhaar application and resident data.
4	Implement policies to correct any security problems		Requesting Entity should implement strong governance and technical security control/ solution (Few example for internet access control are Training and awareness, Developing Acceptable use policy, URL/DNS filtering, Firewall, Network access control, Proxy Server etc.) to restrict, govern and monitor internet access for operator as well as staff to ensure they only have access to white listed or management approved website's over internet using devices leveraged to access or handle Aadhaar authentication device or application or data.
		4.11	Requesting entity should establish an Information Security Policy and Procedures

			addressing the security aspects of Aadhaar as defined under the Aadhaar Act, Regulations and specifications.
5	Limit access to sensitive data	3.12	Privileged accounts such as NTAuthority, Administrator and root accounts shall be accessible to a limited set of users. Access to privileged accounts shall not be allowed to normal users.
		6.8	Entity should ensure only authorised individuals can access information facilities (such as Authentication application, audit logs, authentication servers, application, source code, information security infrastructure etc.) processing Aadhaar related information. Entity should .rr.rr. the access is provided based on least privilege and access should be reviewed periodically.
		6.9	Access rights and privileges to information processing facilities -- for Aadhaar related information shall be revoked within 24 hours of exit of respective personnel. Post deactivation, user IDs shall be deleted if not in use.
6	Monitor for suspicious activity on the network	NA	Not addressed by checklist but by UIDAI's Security Operations Centre